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Research Programme in Tertiary Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

Purpose: This paper examined the problems facing research programmes in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Method: The paper is a review study. The paper depends on secondary data that were collected from government documents, print resources and online publication. Content analysis was used to narrow the literature to the theme of the study.

Findings: The paper discovered that poor funding, shortage of research facilities, poor mentorship, poor synergy between universities and private institutions, weak research institutions, brain drain, insecurity and strike actions are some of the problems facing research programmes in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Recommendations: The government should increase research programme funding in all tertiary institutions to address the poor motivation of researchers and strike issues. The government should reform all agencies saddled with supporting research programmes to be more effective. The government should create a medium where research output will reach the hands of private industries across the country. Modern research infrastructure facilities should be provided in all tertiary institutions. The government should ensure stable light, internet services and adequate security in all tertiary institutions.

Keywords: Research programme, Tertiary institutions

Introduction

Tertiary education is a planned educational system with focus on problem solving through teaching, research and provision of community service (Ogunode, Ayeni, & Ogwuche, 2024a). Tertiary education is an education designed for the production of manpower and providing solutions to societal problems (Ogunode, Ayeni, & Olorundare, 2024). Tertiary education is the education after secondary school meant for manpower training and development and specifically finding solutions to pressing problems in the country at large (Ogunode & Ayeni, 2024).

Tertiary education, also called post-secondary education, is any level of education pursued beyond high school, including undergraduate and graduate credentials. These credentials encompass certificates, diplomas or academic degrees. Tertiary education refers to specialized education in a specific field, taken on after finishing high school. Tertiary education is non-compulsory and provided in a specialist institution, usually a college, polytechnic or university. This form of education may be delivered virtually or at a distance (Top-hat,2023).

Tertiary education is a planned and organized educational system designed for the total development of man/woman and for the total transformation of the society through the utilization of teaching, research and provision of community service (Ogunode, Edinoh & Okolie 2023). Tertiary institution can also be seen as a subset of the general society that is made of the collection of different people, different culture, different life style and different value (Ogunode and Odo 2023). Tertiary education as an educational system that advances the implementation of the teaching programme, research programme and community service programme for the socio-economic and technological development of the country (Ogunode & Mcbrown 2022).

Tertiary education programmes according to Ogunode (2020) includes; teaching, research and community services. Research been the second cardinal programme of the tertiary institutions is critical to their development. Paul (2015) maintained that the conduct of research is one of the basic functions of tertiary institutions, which comprised Universities, Polytechnics, Monothechnics and Colleges of Education. The academic staffs of these institutions are compulsorily required to carry out research activities as their promotions are primarily based on their research outputs. Apart from the academic staff being promoted through research publications, research activities enhance their credibility, status, and also add value both to their immediate community and the larger global community. Ogunode & Abubakar (2020) opined that research is the second cardinal programme of higher institutions. Research is very important to the development of the society. Research is conducted mostly in the higher institutions environment with the objectives to solve problems affecting the society. The academic staff is saddled with the responsibilities of carrying out researches in the universities. Conducting research is one criterion for measuring their performance.....noted that students in tertiary institutions are also compulsorily to carry out researches in their field of specialization as part of the criteria to graduate and complete their programmes.

Research programme in most tertiary institutions across the globe especially in the developing countries appears to be facing a lot of challenges. This paper aims to critically look at the various challenges militating against effective implementation of research programme in the Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Literature Review

Concept of Research

According to the Microsoft Encarta (2009), the prefix re – means again, anew, backward while the word search means to examine something thoroughly that is to look into, over, or through something carefully in order to find something. It also means to discover something by examination -to come to know or find something by examination. When both words are put together, we see research to mean the systematic process of collecting, analyzing and interpreting information concerning a subject matter. Research is often based on two types of definitions: conceptual definition and operational definition according to National Open University (2020) and they includes the following;

i. Conceptual definitions are definitions that describe concepts by using other concepts. As an example, a conceptual definition for “political violence” might be an “aggressive behaviour toward political institutions and persons occupying political roles.” One conceptual definition of “intelligence” might be “the ability to think in an abstract manner.” Another might be “the ability to solve problems.”

ii. Operational definitions attempt to bridge the gap between the theoretical-conceptual level and the empirical observational level. An operational definition involves a series of instructions describing the operations that must be carried out by a researcher in order to demonstrate the existence, or the degree of existence, of an empirical occurrence represented by a concept.

Research can simply be defined as the process of arriving at dependable solutions to problems through planned and systematic collection, analysis and interpretation of data. Research is an important tool for advancing knowledge for promoting progress, and for enabling scholars to relate more effectively to the environment, to accomplish their objectives, and to resolve conflicts (National Open University 2020). Research involves identification of problems, gathering new data, finding solution to a problem through carefully designed procedures and logical analysis (Ogunode, Jegede, Adah, Audu & Ajape 2020). Research according to Echono, (n.d) is an intensive and extensive search for solutions to problems in a society. Others have defined research as the search for knowledge, truth, similarities, and relationships and finding solutions to problems through the systematic collection, analysis, and interpretation of data.

Research is the systematic study of materials and sources in order to establish facts and reach new conclusions (National Open University 2012). Research is the process of creating new knowledge or new insights on knowledge, or unlocking knowledge (Ibidapoobe, 2010). Research ranges from physical thing, an event, a process, a social institution of a social condition, biological condition, etc. Irrespective of the subject, research seeks to understand what is being researched into through observation, experimentation and analysis to arrive at a better understanding or a definite conclusion on the subject matter (Adebola, 2009). Research as a systematic investigation including development, testing and evaluation, designed to develop or to contribute to generalizable knowledge. They further asserted that research is a curiosity-driven activity that has the purpose of discovery and advancement of knowledge (Fawoel, Egbokhare, Itiola, Odejide and Olayinka 2006).

Research is a systematic search and investigation for increasing the sum of knowledge; and research and development (R&D) as the search and application of this knowledge for the development of new and improved products, services and industrial processes of capital development (Bako 2005). Research is an activity that involves observation and description of the characteristic properties of objects or events to discover relationships between variables and developing generalization that may be used to predict future occurrences. Research involves identification of problems, gathering new data, finding solution to a problem through carefully designed procedures and logical analysis (Okeke 2004). Research is the process of arriving at dependable solutions to problems through the planned and systematic collection, analysis, and interpretation of data. Research is oriented towards discovering the relationships that exist among the phenomena of interest to a researcher (Osualla, 2001).

Research involves serious investigation on an issue or programme that needs scientific processes. Romberg (1975) viewed research as its stem “search,” which means ‘look for’ with the prefix ‘re’ which together means ‘to look for again, more carefully, more exhaustively.’ It then means that research has to do with carefully searching out or looking for something to understand whatever one is examining. From above, research is defined in this paper as an investigation into an identified problem and solving the problem through systematic processes. Research is an organized process and investigation that deals with the collection of data problems; the organization of data problems and systematically analyzing collected data by using statistical tools, interpretation of data and presentation of findings. Research is also an

Research is conducted to solve local, national and international pressing problems. National Open University (2020) asserted that research will often argue that a certain individual is “conservative” if he or she answers a series of questions in a specific manner. The assumption is that certain answers to specific questions represent particular personality patterns, one of which is “conservatism.” Research attempts to discover relationships existing among important variables. It is aimed at finding the condition under which a certain phenomenon of interest occurs and the conditions under which it does not occur in what might appear to be similar circumstances.

Research is carried out in both tertiary institutions and research institutions. Research in tertiary institutions according to Yusuf (2012) includes;

i) Individual research: This is initiated and conducted by an individual researcher or a team of researchers who may seek funding from the University Board of Research or from alternative funding agencies, including international organisations, NGOs and the private sector.

(ii) Institutional research: This is initiated and supervised by the institution or a unit of the institution (faculty, department etc) and usually involves a team of researchers. Funding is internal, except where assistance is obtained from external sources.

(iii) Commissioned or contractual research: This is carried out at the instance of an external body, which may be government or a government organ, the private sector, NGOs etc, which also funds the research. The sponsor has right of ownership of the research results.

(iv) Collaborative research: This is a joint research effort with common objectives or goals and involves the sharing of ideas, methodologies, facilities etc between individual researchers or research teams, from the same or different institutions, organisations, countries or regions of the world.

(v) Student research: This is an undergraduate or postgraduate research project undertaken by a student, supervised by the student's department, and the results of which are reported in the student's thesis or dissertation. Student research is usually jointly funded between the student himself (or his sponsor) and his department.

Method

This paper is a position paper. The paper depends on secondary data. The secondary data were collected from print and online publications. Resources related to the topic were collected and content analysis was adopted to screen the kinds of literature to an acceptable size that are needed.

Benefits of the Research Programme

The benefits which accrue from research activities according to Paul (2015) include the following;

Quantitative Education

Quantitative education that makes acquisition of useful skills, desirable values, knowledge, attitudes, ideas and competencies necessary for self-reliance can only be possible through adequate research work. It also results to qualitative instruction, articulate and confident graduates for the society's developmental activities. The quality of the citizens of a country depends on the quality of their education. When research work leads to quality education, the desired manpower required to serve in the various sectors of the economy is guaranteed.

Liberation from Ignorance and Poverty

Research activities and findings liberate man from poverty and ignorance. Research findings can liberate man from the restraints and limitations of ignorance and dependency through exposure. Ignorance and illiteracy are serious leading causes of socioeconomic retrogression and poverty in the countries of the world including Nigeria. The advanced countries of the world like Japan, America, etc, are flourishing economically because of their exposure to research. They are said to be advanced because of the progress they have made in the various fields of human endeavours. No nation in the world has ever thrived on the wings of illiteracy. Adequate research leads to the discovery of new techniques, ideas and ways of doing things which will in turn, lead to wealth creation.

Improvement in Standard of Living

Worthwhile research findings do transform society positively and also improve the overall quality of life. Without research, old knowledge will only be recycled and at a point will become anachronistic. It is important then that research work should show the novelty of ideas and not repetitive but reproductive to have an impact on the life of the society. The variety of results that come from research will expose facts, provide evidence, discover the unknown and ultimately, expand the frontier of knowledge in the different

areas of studies (Emunemu, 2009). All these will improve the standard of living, increase chances of employment, and pave way for economic opportunities and upward social mobility.

Provision of Solutions to Counterparty Problems

When researchers effectively embark upon and complete researches designed to understand and explain various aspects of society or nature, there will be solutions to the social and natural problems that impinge on human well-being in the immediate environment and globally (Ajayi, 2009). Take for instance, the nation can benefit from research findings or discoveries that will provide solutions to some naughty issues like climate change, HIV/AIDS and other related health problems. Through scientific explorations, means of curing myriads of terribly devastating sicknesses and diseases can be discovered and consequently, reduce the mortality rates.

Improvement in Educational Practices

Through research, relevant strategies and methods of learning and teaching new concepts can be learnt from other nations and adapted to improve instructional effectiveness. A lot of changes have taken place in teaching situations today and many more will still take place as long as educational research is being conducted. Educational research is an academic endeavour which is geared towards finding new ways in which the approaches used in providing educational activities in the school system can be improved (Ayodele-Bamisaiye, 2005). Educational research is also conducted to develop new approaches in the professional practice of education in the personality of the learners.

Problem Facing Research Programme in Tertiary Education

Many problems are hindering effective research programmes in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Some of these problems include; poor funding, poor mentorship, poor synergy between universities and private institutions, weak research institutions, brain drain, insecurity, strike actions and a shortage of research facilities.

Poor funding

Inadequate research fund is a major problem facing research programme in the Nigerian public universities. The budgetary allocation for the administration of research programme is not adequate (Ogunode & Ade, 2022; Okolie, 2023). The funds coming into the administration of research from both the government and private institutions is not adequate to develop research in the Nigerian tertiary institutions. Tertiary institutions are poorly funded that is why Udida et al. (2009) and Okebukola (2015) noted that the inability of the Nigerian government to accept and implement the 26% funding formula for education recommended by the UNESCO impact negatively on the performance and sustainability of higher education. Thus, it has become obvious that Nigeria's neglect of the funding formula is detrimental to higher educational institution performance and development aspiration as quality performance is the veritable instrument for sustenance of education system. This neglect has further precipitated crises in the entire higher educational systems as effective teaching; research and service are no longer taking place seriously. Resource constraints and competing priorities are major challenges when it comes to funding research endeavours in developing economies like Nigeria. Resource constraints refer to the limitations imposed by the availability of financial, human, and infrastructural resources. Research, particularly in fields like science, technology, and medicine,

requires substantial financial investment to cover expenses such as equipment, materials, personnel salaries, and administrative costs (Echono, 2023). When funding is limited, researchers often face difficult decisions about which projects to pursue and how to allocate available resources effectively. This can result in potentially groundbreaking research projects being shelved or scaled down due to lack of funding, inhibiting progress and stifling innovation. Competing priorities compound the challenge of funding research. In a world with a myriad of pressing issues, policymakers and funding bodies must make difficult decisions about where to allocate resources. In such scenarios, research projects might struggle to secure funding, particularly if their immediate societal impact is not clear and convincing, or does not align with the priorities of the time (Echono, 2023).

Poor Mentorship

Mentorship is very important in the development and sustainability of research programmes in the universities and it helps to preserve the culture and value of research in the universities. Mentorship provides the platform for young researchers to grow in the research profession. However, poor mentorship in the Nigerian university system have affected the development of research programmes in the various institutions. The relationship between the experienced researchers and the young researchers is not as cordial as before due to many barriers that have crept in to create the gap that is now visible. According to Okebukola (2002), brain drain can be attributed as one of the main reasons for the diminishing scope of mentoring of junior researchers by seasoned and senior researchers. Furthermore, Ola (2012) submitted that many experienced and young lecturers do not see the need in mentoring the junior lecturers and this has affected the quality of research programmes in the universities.

Poor Synergy between Universities and Private Institutions

The poor relationship between research institutes and industries in Nigeria has affected the development of the research output or outcome of various research institutes (Ogunode, 2023). Ikwuakor and Akunna (2022) observed that industry/business support of research in Nigerian universities is relatively non-existent, compared with the level of partnership between industry/business and universities in developed countries. The oil and gas industry, however is an exception, as it provides support in the form of technical workshops, buildings, vehicles, computer hardwares and softwares to affiliated departments of Nigerian universities. But the oil industry can do better by sponsoring and facilitating intentional and strategic research projects that develop local technologies. Among the issues aggravating the inadequate funding of research institutes in Nigeria is the lack of collaboration between the research institutes and the private sector/industries. About 74% of research institutes in Nigeria have no international collaborators, and 61 have no regional or national collaborators (Ragasa et al., 2010).

Weak Research Institutions

There are many public institutions established for carrying out research and many others are to support research programmes in the universities. Many of such institutions are weak. Ikwuakor, and Akunna (2022) concluded that governments play a vital role in research and innovation. They are partners, as well as providers and supporters of resources. Governments also constitute a huge market place for products of

research and innovation. When governments fail to act in any of these capacities, research and innovation falter. This is the case with Nigeria. The Nigerian government has a wonderful science, technology and innovation policy published by the Federal Ministry of Science and Technology (National Science, Technology and Innovation (ST&I) Policy, 2012). If the policy were implemented by 50%, Nigeria would be in a great research position. But that is not the case; the policy appears to be on paper only. Furthermore, bureaucratic bottlenecks persist. The agencies that fund and manage research activities, such as TETFund, Petroleum Technology Development Fund (PTDF), Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), Ministry of Science and Technology, Ministry of Education, and National Universities Commission (NUC) lack proper structure and focus for research procurement and management of their grants. TETFund, for example, grants billions of Naira as interventions for Institutional Based Research (IBR) and National Research Fund (NRF). But these interventions are neither regular nor well managed. The agency lacks research or program managers that one can call anytime and get proper answers. Indexed or catalogued repositories of final reports are either missing, or not made available to the universities, leading to missed collaborative research opportunities. The above inefficiencies, in part, account for little or no return on Nigeria's research investments.

Brain Drain

Brain drain, the emigration of highly skilled and educated individuals from one country to another, has emerged as a significant challenge affecting the funding and progress of research in Nigeria. This phenomenon has been particularly detrimental to the country's ability to develop and sustain a vibrant research ecosystem. As noted by Okunade and Awosusi (2023) migration of skilled researchers and academics seeking better opportunities abroad or what has become popularly known as the Japa syndrome has become a new normal. The current net migration rate for Nigeria in 2023 is -0.273 per 1000 population (Macrotrends, 2023). This syndrome has diverse impacts including on the local research community which faces a shortage of expertise, reduced innovation, and a lack of continuity in critical areas of study.

Insecurity

Insecurity is a major problem affecting the administration of research programme in the Nigerian public universities. Many research programmes in the Nigerian public universities have been put on hold or stopped due to insecurity, especially universities located in the Northern part of Nigeria. Insecurity has prevented the effective administration of school programme in the country (Ogunode et al. 2020b). Many school administrators, teachers, non-teaching staff and students have either been kidnapped or killed (Ogunode, Godwin, and Unoaku, 2021). Ogunode and Abubakar (2020) asserted that the security challenges facing the Nigeria is another challenge preventing effective administration and management of higher institutions in Nigeria. The insurgencies in the Northern part of Nigeria have attacked many higher institutions, disrupting their academic programme, killing students, and destroying infrastructural facilities meant for teaching and learning. Insecurity remains a challenge to research programmes in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria (Ogunode et al. 2021).

Strike Actions

Strike actions by different union groups within public universities in Nigeria are one of the significant challenges facing the administration of research programme in the universities. The refusal of the federal

government to implement the numerous agreements reached with the different trade union groups in the universities has constantly culminated in short-term and long-term industrial actions (Lawan and Ogunode, 2021). During these strike actions, activities within the university grind to a halt and nothing else functions. If an international collaborator had an agreement with a Nigerian scientist to conduct a research in Nigeria and return the results within an agreed time, strike actions will definitely disrupt the flow of research programmes as entry into the university is cut off during the majority of these strike actions (Ogunode et al. 2022; Tomori, 2022).

Shortage of Research Facilities

Inadequate infrastructure presents a significant challenge to funding research in Nigeria. According to the Nigerian Economic Summit Group (2023) of 140 countries ranked on the Global Competitiveness Index in 2019, in terms of infrastructure, Nigeria ranked 133rd, and Nigeria is one of the countries with the worst infrastructure in the world. For research to thrive, a solid infrastructure is essential. In Nigeria, a country with vast potential and a growing research community, the lack of infrastructure poses a significant challenge to funding research initiatives. Inadequate infrastructure hampers research progress in Nigeria and it is imperative to discuss potential solutions to address this challenge. Infrastructure encompasses a wide range of facilities, equipment, and services necessary for researchers to carry out their work effectively (Echono, 2023). This includes laboratories, libraries, high-speed internet, reliable electricity, and transportation systems. Without adequate infrastructure, researchers face numerous obstacles that impede their ability to conduct meaningful research, collaborate with peers, and share their findings with the global scientific community (Echono, 2023).

There are several challenges arising from Lack of Infrastructure according to (Echono, 2023). These includes:

i. Inadequate laboratory facilities. Research, especially in fields such as science, engineering, and medicine, heavily relies on well-equipped laboratories. The absence of state-of-the-art laboratory facilities limits researchers' ability to conduct experiments, analyze data, and make breakthroughs. Second,

ii. limited access to information. Lack of modern libraries and online resources limits researchers' access to up-to-date information, hindering their ability to review existing literature, build upon previous studies, and remain at the forefront of their fields.

iii. Unreliable electricity supply. Frequent power outages disrupt research activities and pose challenges for running experiments, storing sensitive samples, and maintaining essential equipment.

iv. Inadequate internet connectivity. Access to high-speed internet is crucial for collaboration, data sharing, and communication with the global scientific community. Slow or unreliable internet connections hinder researchers' ability to engage in international research networks.

v. Poor transportation systems. Poor transportation systems make it difficult for researchers to travel to conferences, workshops, and collaborative meetings. This isolation limits exposure to new ideas and impedes knowledge exchange (Echono, 2023).

Findings

The paper disclosed that poor funding, shortage of research facilities, poor mentorship, poor synergy between universities and private institutions, weak research institutions, brain-drain, insecurity and strike actions are some of the problems facing research programme in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The finding revealed that poor funding, shortage of research facilities, poor mentorship, poor synergy between universities and private institutions, weak research institutions, brain-drain, insecurity and strike actions are some of the problems facing research programme in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. This findings is in line with the discoveries of Ogunode, Jegede, Adah, Audu & Ajape (2020) and Echono, (2023) they concluded that poor funding, inadequate facilities, corruption, poor research culture, poor relationship between private institutions and research institutions and weak research institutions agencies are major problem militating against research development in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper examined the problems facing research programmes in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paper discovered that poor funding, shortage of research facilities, poor mentorship, poor synergy between universities and private institutions, weak research institutions, brain drain, insecurity and strike actions are some of the problems facing research programmes in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Based on the findings, the paper recommends that the government should increase research programme funding in all tertiary institutions to address poor motivation of researchers and strike issues. The government should reform all agencies saddled with supporting research programmes to be more effective. Government should create a medium where research output will reach the hands of private industries across the country. Modern research infrastructure facilities should be provided in all tertiary institutions. The government should ensure stable light, internet services and adequate security in all tertiary institutions.

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